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Fruit Identification and Nutritional Analysis of Indigenous Indian Fruits Using MobileNetV2 emphasizing Vitamin C and Potassium

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ABSTRACT

Image identification has been revolutionized by progressions in computer vision and deep learning. Nutritional analysis, accurate identification, examination of twelve distinctive indigenous fruits by an architecture known as MobileNetV2: fig, guava, pineapple, cherry, mango, tamarillo, apple, banana, mulberry, carambola, are the objectives of this research. MobileNetV2 is particularly relevant for deployment on resource-limited devices, which is applicable in real-time applications in the food and agriculture sectors, due to its computational efficiency. Our model uses transfer learning from the ImageNet database in order to accurately classify such fruits highlighting extraction of nutritional information mainly vitamin C & potassium. The model accuracy had a big improvement during training with training loss decreasing from 1.2984 to 0.0482 across 20 epochs while accuracy went up to 98.44%. For consumers who want healthy eating habits, this tool provides an easy way access information on nutrition labels found on various fruits which goes a long way in helping them choose what they want at the same time in the world of foods things have got easier because fruit recognition has been automated thus maintaining uniformity during labeling as well as accuracy regarding nutrition facts.

Keywords:-Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Deep Learning, Identification, Nutrition

1. INTRODUCTION

In computer vision with deep learning, there have been unparalleled advances with CNNs profoundly impacting how we assess and categorize images. In this context identifying fruits presents an important opportunity; with its use in agricultural, food quality evaluations or dieting. Different stakeholders, including consumers, nutritionists and food processors, need accurate identification of fruits alongside what they contain nutritionally. This study focuses on harnessing the capabilities of the MobileNetV2 architecture for both precise fruit identification and comprehensive retrieval of nutritional information, with a specific emphasis on 10 indigenous Indian fruits: Apple (*Malus domestica*), Banana (*Musa acuminata*), Carambola (*Averrhoa carambola*), Cherry (*Prunus avium*), Fig (*Ficus carica*), Guava (*Psidium guajava*), Mango (*Mangifera indica*), Mulberry (*Morus nigra*), Pineapple (*Ananas comosus*), and Tamarillo (*Solanum betaceum*). These fruits origin is India and most popular in diets also because of their nutritional significance.

Its energy efficient architecture makes MobileNetV2 quite palpable for use in environments such as mobile devices and embedded systems with limited resources. Therefore, it efficiently utilizes computational power while balancing accuracy for real-time applications and scaling across various platforms. In our work, we taken reference knowledge of ImageNet database using MobileNetV2, this makes our model able to identify fruits accurately.

Apart from visual identifiers, our study is centered around the nutritional contents of these fruits, with particular emphasis on Vitamin C and Potassium that are present in noticeable quantities across different types. In fruits, Vitamin C, which acts as an antioxidant and plays an important role in immune defense and production of collagen, varies greatly and is essential in our diet for the purpose of maintaining good health.

Furthermore, Potassium helps in the handling of fluids, the operation of muscles, and the transmission of signals by nerves, and it is found in fruits in large amounts like other important minerals to human health. This study's dedication to promoting balanced diets also favorable health patterns among Indian people shown by the presence of these precise nutrition markers.

Our study is important beyond the thought of academic curiosity; it has practical significance in many areas. Our system provides a user-friendly interface enabling consumers reach nutritive composition of native Indian plants; therefore, making them make healthy eating choices. Automated fruit identification within the food industry improves on quality standards through ensuring that there is uniformity in product labelling and accuracy on information about fruits which are indigenous. Furthermore, the research results could be used in creating educational resources for improving understanding of nutrition hence enhancing healthier dietary behaviour that align with local food habits.

In this paper, We discussed expansively about present methods used for identifying fruits, analyzing their nutrients. We would narrow our attention only on studies that are related to our country's fruits i.e., examples being; those that talk only about Vitamin C or Potassium aspect among others. Next, our research method is explored, including how we collected the data, prepared the data, selected the model structure, optimized training strategies, and specifically fruits and calories. The paper shows that this research work can help in identifying fruits as quickly as possible and returning nutritional information about them. Finally, we discuss the broader implications of our findings, conclusion, and outline future research directions to further advance this field.

2. SURVEY OF LITERATURE

Deep learning methodologies have changed fruit identification and analysis significantly

in recent years. Gulzar created an innovative fruit image classification model utilizing MobileNetV2, deep transfer learning for considerable improvements in categorizing various kinds of fruits with great accuracy [1]. This advancement highlights how important deep learning is when it comes to enhancing fruit classification procedures helping companies to come up with better quality control techniques in agriculture and food businesses at large. This automatized system created by Amin et al. uses CNNs merged with transfer learning enabling immediate appraisal of fruit conditions through visual features derived from images [2].

Pawar's team relied on deep learning models like CNNs and LSTM networks to use neural network models that can recognize diseases and further classify them in various fruits. Therefore, them looking at ways we can act fast were considered of as interventions since they would prevent the risk of loss due to plant destruction or poor production, this would lead to sustainable farming types [3]. In addition, an extensive literature search was done by Espinoza et al. to get information on the latest development of fruit disease analysis systems. Their review reveals substantial progress in automated disease diagnosis systems heightening the ability to understand diseases related to various fruits by using deep learning methods for diagnostic purposes [4]. "Substantial progress has been seen recently in automated disease diagnosis systems," report the authors, "signalling increased reliability and scalability of deep learning systems with respect to detection of different types of fruit diseases through image-based diagnostics" [4].

Nguyen and Yan examined a recent concept of examining fruit quality using deep learning techniques in their study. In particular, it was founded on broader strategies for grading fresh fruits incorporating visual features created from pictures in objective evaluation of various grades of the quality of these products [5].

Mukhiddinov et al. made even better an improved classification approach for different types of fruits and vegetables. They emphasized the significance of machine vision and deep learning in improving the quality control of products which may alter product standards in the food industry [6].

In food image identification and nutritional analysis, deep learning has been considered for use by Mansouri et al. along with its profound effect on tailored dietary assessment and long-term illness tracking. As noted, the review showed the ease with which one can extract accurate nutritional profiles from food images through deep learning techniques hence allowing for personalized nutritional advice [7]. To advance fruit research, the authors show that deep learning allows a range of applications to improve agriculture through better disease classification as well as higher accuracy in quality identification and nutritional analysis.

This recent study updates existing literature that identifies fruit using deep learning approaches to include previously overlooked parts. Ours is an innovative approach that redefines techniques through amalgamating different imaging styles like multispectral into the typical RGB-centered CNNs also transfer learning as adopted by other scholarly contributions. Hence this research paper improves findings shown that more information is required to build resilient models, which may integrate similar biochemical and nutrient contents. Consequently, he deduced that at low levels of mammal diversity; species differed in their ability to exploit economic resources. Also in case of interpretability, more emphasis is directed towards creating AI frameworks that would expound on how fruits are identified. Therefore, in linking nutrition impact analysis with feature attribution methods, the aim is to make the models more trustworthy and transparent in real tasks and with it paves way for an alternative definition of knowledge.

Our research optimizes model architecture for low-latency inference and explores lightweight CNN alternatives deployed on edge devices to bridge this gap in real-time processing for the purpose of practical applications in farming or food industry. Finally, we propose new evaluation criteria that take into account the variety of fruit characteristics and environmental conditions to provide a broader view of the effectiveness of the model in different functional domains. Consequently, our method intends to bring about the development of fruit recognition technologies by linking up technical revolution with its implementation through

promoting interdisciplinary cooperation among agriculturalists, nutritionists, and computer scientists.

3. DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The section below outlines the process followed in building and testing an AI model, trained through deep learning to recognize and identify 10 fruits originating from India; figure 1 shows some instantiate stages. We used MobileNetV2 for transfer learning in building the architecture and several task-specific stages including data preparation, training the model, tuning it for accuracy as well assessing performance (fine-tuning).

Fig.1:-Block Diagram of the Design Methodology

The dataset D consists of images of 10 distinct Indian-origin fruits: Apple, Banana, Carambula, Cherry, Fig, Guava, Mango, Mulberry, Pineapple, and Tamarillo. Each fruit category I within D is represented as D_i , containing images. The dataset is carefully curated to ensure diversity in fruit variations, orientations, and environmental conditions. We resize all images contained in D to 224x224 pixels and correct the pixel values to have a range between 0 and 1. Rotate, translate, flip, zoom and crop techniques are some of the techniques used to add data to the Image Data Generator found in the TensorFlow Keras API. Doing so tends to

boost the size of our dataset, besides enhancing our model's ability to generalize. The base architecture for our identification task is the MobileNetV2 model that is pretrained on the ImageNet dataset. It utilizes depthwise separable convolutions which help in lowering computational complexity without sacrificing accuracy. Primary layers comprise of an initial convolutional layer preceded by a sequence of inverted residual blocks having linear bottlenecks, and ending with global average pooling followed by a dense softmax identification layer.

Initially, the base layers of MobileNetV2 are frozen to retain learned features during training. The model is developed with the

Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss function:

$$\min_{\theta}^{\text{custom}} \frac{1}{|D_{\text{train}}|} \sum_{(x_i, y_i) \in D_{\text{train}}} L(f_{\text{custom}}(x_i; \theta_{\text{custom}}), y_i)$$

where L denotes categorical cross-entropy loss. Training of the model is conducted over N epochs with B as the batch size.

To refine the model, the last 50 layers of MobileNetV2 are unfrozen, and the entire network is fine-tuned with a reduced learning rate:

$$\min_{\theta}^{\text{fine-tuned}} \frac{1}{|D_{\text{train}}|} \sum_{(x_i, y_i) \in D_{\text{train}}} L(\text{fine-tuned}(x_i; \theta_{\text{fine-tuned}}), y_i)$$

The performance of the trained model is evaluated on the testing dataset D_{test} . Evaluation metrics include:

Accuracy: It is calculated as the proportion of correctly identified fruit images out of the entire test set. This performance metric is determined by the sum of model expectation errors for each instance in the test set.

Loss: A value that indicates how wrong model predictions are based on individual errors for every instance in the test set.

Precision: It refers to the instances where the prediction of an apple was correct among all cases where any fruit was predicted to be an apple. when you're able to accurately spot 80% of apples without creating false positives like pears, your precision ratio would be 0. The ratio can be written as: (True Positive / All Predicted Positive)

Recall: it's the portion of all cases with true labels plus we predicted as positive.

F1-score: It calculates the harmonic mean of precision and recall to offer a singular evaluation of the model's overall efficacy.

The confusion matrix is computed to visualize and analyze identification errors, providing visualization to the model's performance across different fruit categories.

Calories, Carbohydrates, Fiber, Sugar, Vitamin C, Potassium and other minerals information is sourced from reliable nutritional databases like USDA National Nutrient Database and Indian Food Composition Tables (IFCT) for any classified fruit. Thus, retrieval process entails matching classified fruit with its corresponding entry in the database and getting the right nutritional particulars. Special emphasis is placed on Vitamin C and Potassium, given their significant presence and health implications.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The training process of the MobileNetV2-based model on the augmented dataset of India-origin fruits demonstrated significant improvements in accuracy and reductions in loss over the course of 20 epochs. The results shown graphically in figure 2. The training accuracy steadily increased to a peak of 98.44%, Showing that the model accurately learned to distinguish between different fruit types. Simultaneously, the training loss decreased from 1.2984 to a minimal value of 0.0482, reflecting the model's ability to minimize errors during training.

Fig.2:-Visualization of Model Accuracy and Loss

The training data confusion matrix will give detailed separation of model performance over ten categories Indian origin fruits with each cell in the matrix showing the count of predictions, rows indicating actual classes while columns show the predicted ones. This chart displayed shown in figure 3

facilitates the assessment of the model's effectiveness in distinguishing different fruit types, highlighting areas where misidentifications may occur and identifying which fruit types are most easily confused with others.

Fig.3:-Confusion Matrix of Trained Data

Users could post test images to the system for live identification of fruits. Once a image was uploaded (See figure 4), the model applied weights that had been learned previously in order for it to recognize which type of fruit was shown together with

specific nutritional information pertaining to this item such as calories, carbohydrates, fibre or sugars per serving which makes them able to get useful nutritional facts about any symbol they observe fruits in.

Fig.4:-GUI to upload an Test Image and Outcome

A comparative graph shown in figure 5 was plotted to display the training and testing accuracies over the 20 epochs. This graph provides a clear depiction of how model generalized to unseen test data compared to

its performance on the training set. It shows trends in accuracy improvement or stabilization, highlighting any overfitting or underfitting issues that may affect the model's performance in real-world scenarios.

Fig.5:-Comparison of Training and Testing Accuracies

The identification report offers a detailed evaluation of the model's performance on the test dataset. It includes metrics such as precision, recall, F1-score, and support for each fruit class, providing a comprehensive analysis of the model's ability to correctly

classify varieties of fruits as shown in table 1. These metrics are essential for understanding the model's strengths and weaknesses in identifying specific fruit categories, helping to assess its overall effectiveness in practical applications.

Table 1:-Classification Report of Fruits

Fruits/metrics	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Apple	1.00	0.83	0.91	144
Banana	1.00	1.00	1.00	301
Carambula	1.00	1.00	1.00	166
Cherry	1.00	0.79	0.88	317
Fig	1.00	0.97	0.99	234
Guava	1.00	1.00	1.00	166
Mango	0.91	0.99	0.95	289

Mulberry	1.00	1.00	1.00	164
Pineapple	1.00	1.00	1.00	294
Tamrillo	0.71	1.00	0.83	166
accuracy			0.96	2241
macro avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	2241
weighted avg	0.97	0.96	0.96	2241

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The current paper will examine the use of MobileNetV2 in identifying fruits and retrieving nutrition details of ten Indian local fruits. Our model attained a high rate of accuracy in identifying the types of fruits by utilizing transfer learning methods as well as the most recent increase in data variations during the training session; hence, it presents some essential profiles required in dietetics instead. Real-time recognition capabilities integration makes food industry usability better by supporting well-informed consumer choice and food quality control. The value of this study is improved deep learning which helps resolve such difficult things as classification for fruits or food nutrition analysis thus enabling intelligent dietary tools to be applied in health monitoring systems and consumer training.

Future studies may investigate how robust and scalable the model might become across a broader variety of fruits and environmental conditions. Besides, the generalization capabilities of the model could be improved by expanding the data set to incorporate additional diverse varieties together with nutritional markers. Moreover, if the model is optimized for use on edge devices and interpretability techniques are studied, agriculture and dietary management applications can be realized in real-time workings. Additionally, agricultural experts and nutritionists need to collaborate so as to enhance the model thus boosting interdisciplinary progressions in fruit recognition technologies that meet the specific dietary preferences also health needs of different regions.

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